

ORIGINAL PAPER

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Improving mechanical and barrier properties of cold-water fish gelatin films through sodium alginate and gellan reinforcement for food packaging applications

Tra Thi Thanh Nguyen¹, Izumi Sone² and Nusrat Sharmin^{3*}

Abstract

Cold-water fish gelatin (FG, 5% w/v) was combined with sodium alginate (SA) and gellan (GL) at concentrations of 0.01, 0.05, and 0.1% (v/v) to prepare composite FG films using casting method. The mechanical and barrier (water vapor transmission rate) properties of resulting films were characterized while the film-forming solutions were analyzed using a rheometer and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). The addition of GL and SA, regardless of concentration, improved barrier properties. GL increased the tensile strength (TS) without affecting the elongation at break (EB), whereas a high concentration of SA (0.1% v/v) led to an improvement in the EB. The viscoelastic behavior of FG film-forming solutions improved with the addition of GL at 0.05 and 0.1% (v/v), whereas SA showed only negligible effects. The FTIR analysis showed a shift in amide I peak to a higher wavenumber in the presence of GL (0.05 and 0.1% v/v), indicating changes in the secondary structures of FG mixtures and their effects on film properties.

Keywords Fish gelatin, Gellan, Sodium alginate, Sustainable packaging

Introduction

Food packaging contributes to food safety and preservation (Raheem 2013). Plastic packaging materials such as polyethylene, polypropylene, polyethylene terephthalate are difficult to biodegrade leading to their persistent accumulation in the environment (Raheem 2013; Ncube et al. 2021; Nilsen-Nygaard et al. 2021). Thus, finding an

environmentally friendly alternative for food packaging is an urgent need. Fish gelatin (FG), obtained from fish skin, scales, and bones, is a promising raw material for food packaging due to its biodegradability, film-forming ability, and its suitability as an alternative to traditional bovine and porcine gelatins, which pose health and religious concerns (Sohar 2012; Razzak et al. 2016). FG, especially cold-water FG, is characterized by its elevated content of hydrophobic amino acid, which can lower the water vapour permeability compared with warm-water fish and mammalian gelatin (Avena-Bustillos et al. 2006; Chiou et al. 2008). However, cold-water FG has not been widely used due to its inherent limitations (Chung 2020; Yang et al. 2012). For instance, the strength of cold-water FG films is often lower than that of mammalian and warm-water fish gelatin due to low levels of imino acids

*Correspondence:

Nusrat Sharmin

Nusrat.Sharmin@nofima.no

¹Department of Chemistry, Bioscience and Environmental Engineering, University of Stavanger, 4021 Stavanger, Norway

²Department of Processing Technology, Nofima AS, 4021 Stavanger, Norway

³Department of Food Safety and Quality, Nofima AS, Osloveien 1, 1430 Ås, Norway

(proline and hydroxyproline) (Yang et al. 2012; Gómez-Guillén et al. 2009). Approximately 30% and 17% of proline and hydroxyproline, respectively, were found in mammalian and cold-water FG (Chung 2020). Since the triple helix structure of gelatin is stabilized by the repeating glycine–X–Y sequence, in which X and Y are frequently imino acids, a higher imino acid content generally enhances rigidity (Said and Sarbon 2022). To address the drawbacks of cold-water FG films, one promising strategy is blending with polysaccharides, which can promote polysaccharide–protein interactions and improve overall film properties (Shi et al. 2022; Pranoto et al. 2007). Gelatin, a polyelectrolyte complex, includes positively and negatively charged groups, as well as hydroxyl and hydrophobic groups. At pH slightly higher than the gelatin's isoelectric point (pI), gelatin will interact with ionic polysaccharides by intermolecular electrostatic interactions and hydrogen bonds (Derkach et al. 2020; Al-Harrasi et al. 2022). Polysaccharides such as SA and GL have shown potential for enhancing FG matrices. When tilapia FG gel was incorporated with SA at concentrations ranging from 0.05 to 0.4% (w/v), both the gel strength and hardness of FG increased (Sow et al. 2019a). Similarly, GL increased the gel strength and hardness of cold-water FG and GL composite gels, due to the formation of more interconnected, denser and finer gel network upon heating (Petcharat and Benjakul 2018). The addition of GL (2 g/100 g) to tilapia FG film-forming solutions increased the TS and barrier properties of blend films (Pranoto et al. 2007). Similarly, the TS of tilapia FG films increased with the incorporation of SA (up to 8 g/L) (Chen et al. 2024). Blending with polysaccharides can enhance the structural integrity and uniformity of composite gelatine films by eliminating cracks and particles within the film matrix (Pranoto et al. 2007; Al-Harrasi et al. 2022). However, studies on the properties of composite films made from polysaccharides and proteins are still limited (Al-Harrasi et al. 2022; Lee et al. 2004; Dou et al. 2018). From our literature studies, most research has focused on the interactions between polysaccharides and mammalian gelatin or warm-water FG, leaving a gap in understanding the functional properties of cold-water FG. Additionally, previous studies have generally examined FG-based films and FG solutions separately, with very little research connecting the properties of solutions to those of the resulting solid films. To address these gaps, the present study investigated whether blending cold-water FG with two different polysaccharides (SA and GL) at varying concentrations (0.01, 0.05, and 0.1% v/v) could enhance the mechanical, barrier properties of resulting films, as well as the rheological properties of cold-water FG solutions.

Material and methods

Materials

Cold-water FG was purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Canada. Glycerol, sourced from Sigma Aldrich, Malaysia was used as a plasticizer. Gellan (GL) was obtained from Sigma Aldrich, Germany. Additionally, sodium alginate (SA) was supplied by Sigma Aldrich, China.

Fish gelatin-based film preparation

Pristine FG solution was prepared in distilled water by stirring at 350 rpm overnight at room temperature. It was then heated at 60 °C for 25 min in the water bath with continuous mechanical agitation. A 1% GL stock solution (w/v) was prepared in distilled water by stirring continuously on a magnetic stirrer (MR Hei-Tec, Heidolph Instrument, Germany) at 600 rpm overnight at room temperature. The solution was heat-treated at 90 °C for 5 min in a water bath to ensure complete dissolution and cooled to 60 °C for further use. A 1% SA stock solution (w/v) was prepared in distilled water and stirred at 550 rpm for about 1 h at room temperature until fully dissolved. To prepare for blending FG-GL and -SA formulations, appropriate volume of GL and SA solutions were added to the FG solutions to reach the final concentrations of 0.01, 0.05, 0.1% (v/v) and stirred for 5 min. The concentration of the pristine FG solution was adjusted to achieve the final concentration of 5% (w/v) in the mixture. Glycerol was added at 30% (w/w) of the gelatine, and the mixture was stirred for an additional 5 min. Films were prepared by the casting method as described by Sharmin et al. (2023) (Pažarauskaitė et al. 2023). 20 mL of the film-forming solution was poured into a 90 mm polystyrene petri dish and left to dry for 5 days at room temperature without the petri dish lid.

Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of films were measured using TA.XT Plus texture analyzer equipped with a 30 kg loading cell (Stable Micro Systems Ltd., Godalming, UK), following the method of Dysjaland et al. (2022) with slight modification (Dysjaland et al. 2022). The film was cut into rectangular strips of 60 mm × 15 mm and film thickness was measured using a digital caliper (Hand-Hold Limit Digital Caliper, Limit, United Kingdom) at three different positions. The film stripe was mounted between the tensile grips (Stable Micro Systems Ltd., Godalming, UK) with a span distance of 25 cm and stretched until breakage at the rate of 0.85 mm/s. At least 5 replicates were prepared. The maximum force (N) at break and the distance at maximum force (mm) were obtained from the software Exponent (ver. 8.0.11.0, Stable Micro Systems Ltd). Tensile strength (TS) and elongation at break (EB) were calculated as below equations (Dysjaland et al. 2022):

$$TS (MPa) = \frac{Max\ tensile\ force}{Length \times Thickness} \quad (1)$$

$$EB (\%) = \frac{Distance\ at\ max\ tensile\ force}{Distance\ between\ grips} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

Water vapor transmission rate (WVTR)

The WVTR of the films were conducted gravimetrically, following ASTM 15.09: E96 (International 1983). Films were sealed mechanically onto Vapometer cells, containing 20.0 g of anhydrous calcium chloride (0% RH). Initially, the cells were weighed and placed inside a humidity room at 23 °C and 50% RH. The weight of cells was measured again after 24 h. Experiments were performed in triplicate. The weight gain of the cell is presented as the amount of water vapor transferred through the film and absorbed by the desiccant. The maximum weight gain was limited to 10% to maintain the accuracy of the results (Khan et al. 2012). The WVTR was calculated by the below equation (Pažarauskaitė et al. 2023):

$$WVTR = \frac{w_i - w_t}{A \times T} \times gm^{-2}day^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where A is the surface area (m²), T is time (day), W_i and W_t are the weight of cells at the beginning and after 24 h, respectively (g).

Rheological properties

A Hybrid Rheometer (Discovery HR-2, TA Instruments, Newcastle, UK) equipped with a 40 mm parallel plate was used. Film-forming solution was cooled down to room temperature following heat treatment. ~650 μL of the sample was loaded onto the Peltier plate and

held at 22 °C for 10 min. To limit evaporation, deionized water was placed in the solvent trap on the upper parallel plate. The geometry was then lowered to the gap distance of 450 μm. The temperature of the Peltier plate was cooled down to 4 °C at the rate of 1 °C/min with axial force adjustment. The sample at 4 °C was subjected to a frequency sweep ranging from 0.01 to 0.5 Hz at a constant strain of 0.5%, as well as strain sweeps ranging from 0.01 to 1000% at a constant frequency of 0.1 Hz, with five points per decade. Storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') were recorded by TRIOS software ver.5.6 (TA Instruments, Newcastle, UK). The critical strain was defined as the strain at which the G' decreased to 90% of its previous value (Zhu et al. 2019). Each sample was analyzed in triplicates.

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) analysis

FTIR spectra of film forming solutions were obtained using Bruker INVENIO Spectrometer (Bruker Optics, Germany) equipped with a high-throughput extension HTS-XT. The software OPUS ver. 8.5 was utilized to control the data acquisition process. The sample solution was filled with thin layers on 96-well Silicon plates. The spectral data was obtained through the transmission mode in the range 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. Five replicates were made for each sample. The number of scans was 40 times. UnscramblerTM v11 (Camo Analytics AS, Oslo, Norway) software was used for baseline correction and calculating the average of five replicates.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software (SPSS statistics, version 29.0.1.1, IBM) with one-way analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA). Tukey's B post hoc test was conducted when appropriate. Statistical significance was set at P < 0.05.

Results and discussion

Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of FG films were significantly influenced by types and concentrations of polysaccharides added (Table 1). The addition of GL improved the TS with increasing concentration, with the highest concentration (0.1% v/v) doubling the TS of FG films. In contrast, the addition of SA at 0.1% (v/v) significantly decreased the film TS by 61%. On the other hand, the incorporation of SA or GL did not significantly influence the EB of FG films, except with SA at 0.1% (v/v) where the EB reached ~97%. This finding aligns with those of Pranoto et al. (2007) who reported an 8% increase in the TS and no significant change in the EB in tilapia FG films after adding GL (1 g/100 g gelatin granules) to 5% (w/v) FG film-forming solutions at pH ~ 6 (Pranoto et al. 2007). The pH of FG/GL film-forming solution was

Table 1 Summary of thickness, tensile strength (TS), elongation at break (EB), and water vapor transmission rate (WVTR) of cold-water fish gelatin films (FG) with and without different concentrations of polysaccharides. Different letters present values that are significantly different (p < 0.05)

	Thickness (mm)	TS (Mpa)	EB (%)	WVTR (g.mm ⁻² h ⁻¹)
FG	0.16 ± 0.02 ^{bcd}	29.15 ± 16.06 ^b	6.69 ± 0.58 ^a	5.56 ± 0.69 ^b
0.01% SA	0.17 ± 0.03 ^{cd}	20.96 ± 6.00 ^{ab}	6.67 ± 0.58 ^a	4.74 ± 0.22 ^b
0.05% SA	0.14 ± 0.03 ^{abc}	27.51 ± 6.23 ^b	6.35 ± 0.69 ^a	3.47 ± 0.30 ^a
0.1% SA	0.18 ± 0.01 ^d	11.26 ± 1.11 ^a	97.02 ± 17.08 ^b	4.77 ± 0.33 ^b
0.01% GL	0.13 ± 0.01 ^{ab}	53.32 ± 1.94 ^c	6.50 ± 0.59 ^a	5.77 ± 0.04 ^b
0.05% GL	0.13 ± 0.01 ^a	55.37 ± 5.95 ^c	7.07 ± 0.91 ^a	4.72 ± 0.04 ^b
0.1% GL	0.13 ± 0.00 ^{ab}	64.44 ± 4.82 ^c	6.68 ± 0.82 ^a	4.87 ± 0.57 ^b

pH \sim 5.1 in this study. Chen et al. (2024) demonstrated that warm-water FG and chitosan exhibited the strongest electrostatic interaction at pH \sim 5, forming stable complexes (Cheng et al. 2023). The increase of the TS of FG/GL films could be due to the enhanced electrostatic interaction between anion groups of GL and cation groups of FG observed at similar pH range. However, the optimum pH for electrostatic interaction in cold-water FG/SA solutions was reported to be pH \sim 3.7 (Razzak et al. 2016; Sow et al. 2019a). Derkach et al. (2021) reported that no coacervation occurred when mixing 10 wt.% cold-water FG with 0.2–2 wt.% SA at pH values between 5.2 and 5.9 (Derkach et al. 2021). In this study, the pH of the FG/SA solutions was approximately 5.3, indicating that the conditions were not favorable for electrostatic interactions between FG and SA. This may contribute to the reduction of TS in the FG films with the addition of SA. At high SA concentration (0.1% v/v), SA could absorb moisture from the surrounding environment, causing the film to swell. This swelling increases the free volume within the film structure, allowing greater mobility of the polymer chains. Furthermore, high concentration of SA could lead to increase the total hydrophilicity of the film, which can attract more water molecules transmit through the film (Chen et al. 2024). The increased flexibility can enhance the mobility, which could explain the observed increase in EB (Caicedo et al. 2022). Additionally, TS and EB have an inverse relationship, EB reaches its highest value when TS is at its lowest (Ghasemi et al. 2021). In this experiment, the lowest TS value was observed in the FG film containing 0.1% SA, which also showed the highest EB. This trend aligns with findings by Rivero et al. (2010), who reported that when the TS of bovine gelatin films with plasticizer decreased 11 times, the EB increased 61 times compared to unplasticized samples (Rivero et al. 2010). The film thickness also plays a vital role in the mechanical properties of FG based-films (Nurdiani et al. 2022). As shown in Table 1, the addition of GL generally led to a significant reduction in FG films' thickness. Pure FG films had a thickness of 0.16 mm, which reduced to 0.13 mm when GL was added. This reduction may be explained by interactions between GL and FG, leading to a more compact structure with fewer voids, which in turn contributed to the observed increase in TS with GL addition. However, the thickness of films fluctuated with SA addition. At 0.01% and 0.1% SA, the thickness increased to 0.17 and 0.18 mm, respectively, likely due to reduced compactness of the film structure compared to pure FG based-films (0.16 mm). However, at 0.05% SA, the thickness decreased to 0.14 mm, possibly reflecting stronger FG–SA interactions at this specific concentration, which is consistent with the higher TS observed compared to the other SA concentrations.

Water vapor transmission rate (WVTR)

Table 1 shows the WVTR of FG films with and without addition of GL and SA at different concentrations. The GL addition improved the barrier properties of FG films against water vapor, reducing the WVTR by 18% and 14% on average with 0.05% and 0.1% (v/v) GL, respectively. The reduction in WVTR may be attributed to the electrostatic interaction between negative charge from carboxyl group of GL to positive charge from amino acid including arginine, lysine, and histidine of FG, which creates a denser structure and prevents water penetration (Sae-leaw et al. 2016; Hagenmaier 2012; Sarabia et al. 2000). Additionally, the presence of GL may have reduced the free volume within FG films, leading to more compact and dense internal structure (Pranoto et al. 2007). According to Hagenmaier et al. (2012), gas migration through a sealed plastic bag occurs via a permeance mechanism. In this process, gas molecules first dissolve into one side of the barrier, diffuse through the material, and then exit from the opposite side of the plastic bag (Hagenmaier 2012). Therefore, any factor that impedes this gas migration can effectively reduce the material's permeability. The WVTR of FG films generally decreased with SA addition, indicating enhanced barrier properties. FG films with 0.05% (v/v) SA exhibited the lowest WVTR, making a significant 39% reduction compared to that of pristine FG films. According to Table 1, films containing SA are thicker, leading to a longer diffusion path for water vapor, therefore a lower WVTR. Derkach et al. (2020) reported the formation of additional nodes within the structural network of bovine gelatin gels with SA at 0.2 to 2 wt.% which may have prevented the movement of water molecules (Derkach et al. 2020). However, WVTR tends to slightly increase in FG films with the introduction of 0.1% SA (v/v) compared to that of 0.05% SA (v/v) addition. The increase in the WVTR could be due to the plasticization effect at high SA concentration, making films more flexible but less dense, resulting in higher WVTR (Caicedo et al. 2022). The same decreasing trend of WVTR was observed in the study of Chen et al. (2024). When they prepared FG from Tilapia fish with SA, they suggested that low concentration of SA improved the water vapor barrier performance of FG films which was the opposite with high concentration of SA. Particularly, the WVP reduced from 2.25 ± 0.23 g. mm/m².h kPa in pure FG films (100 g/L) to 1.91 ± 0.23 g. mm/m².h kPa with the addition of low concentration of SA (2 g/L). However, when high concentration of SA (4 g/L) was added, the WVP increased up to 2.75 ± 0.16 g. mm/m².h kPa (Chen et al. 2024). These results are in line with mechanical testing where TS decreased significantly while EB increased dramatically at FG – 0.1% SA films. However, the WVTR of the 0.1% SA containing films was still 16% lower than the pure FG films. Therefore, it could

be concluded that films containing 0.05% SA showed the lowest WVTR, meaning the films with the best water vapor barrier properties. Moreover, the water vapor barrier of FG films could be improved with the modification with GL and SA, but this depends on the concentration added.

Rheological properties

Figure 1 shows representative curves of storage- (G') (A) and loss modulus (G'') (B) of FG film-forming

solutions with SA and GL in the frequency range from 0.01 to 0.5 Hz at constant strain 0.5%. The addition of GL enhanced the G' of FG solutions at increasing concentrations. The FG solution with 0.1% GL showed a lower rate of frequency-dependent increase in G' compared to the pristine FG solutions and those with GL at the lower concentrations. This suggests the formation of a stable, cross-linked structure with higher GL concentration as GL acted as an active filler in the gel network and formed stronger interactions between the two

Fig. 1 Representative curves of storage modulus (G') [A] and loss modulus (G'') [B] of FG film-forming solutions with and without addition of SA and GL at concentrations 0.01, 0.05, and 0.1% (v/v) in the frequency range of 0.01 to 0.5 Hz at 0.5% constant strain

Fig. 2 Representative curves of storage modulus (G') of FG film-forming solutions with and without addition of SA and GL at concentrations 0.01, 0.05, and 0.1% (v/v), measured over an oscillatory strain range of 0.01% to 1000% at a constant frequency of 0.1 Hz and temperature of 4 °C

Table 2 The critical strains of FG solutions with and without addition of SA and GL at concentrations 0.01, 0.05, and 0.1% (v/v). Different letters present values that are significantly different ($p < 0.05$)

Sample	Critical strain (%)	G' at critical strain (Pa)
FG	10.00 ± 0.00 ^b	0.05 ± 0.02 ^a
0.01% GL	3.99 ± 0.01 ^a	0.14 ± 0.03 ^{ab}
0.05% GL	8.79 ± 2.14 ^b	0.20 ± 0.07 ^b
0.1% GL	10.03 ± 0.02 ^b	0.45 ± 0.02 ^c
0.01% SA	11.95 ± 3.38 ^a	0.04 ± 0.01 ^a
0.05% SA	10.00 ± 0.00 ^a	0.05 ± 0.01 ^a
0.1% SA	10.00 ± 0.00 ^a	0.08 ± 0.01 ^a

molecules (Petcharat and Benjakul 2018; Sinthusamran et al. 2017). This accounted for the higher G' and G'' values of FG film-forming solutions with GL, in agreement with the improved mechanical properties of GL-incorporated FG films. On the other hand, the addition of SA had a minimal impact on the viscoelastic properties of FG/SA solutions compared to the pure FG solutions. A slight reduction in G' and G'' was observed at low SA concentrations (0.01% and 0.05% v/v), corresponding to the decreasing trend observed for TS of FG films (Fig. 1). According to Kolotova et al., 2023, the charges of the mixture of Atlantic cod skin FG and SA is almost complete neutralization in the pH range of 5 to 6, resulting in the formation of insoluble complexes (Kolotova et al. 2023). With similar pH of FG/SA film-forming solutions (~pH 5) in this study, it is possible that the formation of

insoluble complexes in FG/SA film-forming solutions may have contributed to the slight reduction in the rheological properties and strength of composite films.

Figure 2 and Table 2 presents G' of FG film-forming solutions with and without GL and SA under increasing strain from 1 to 1000% at constant frequency 0.1 Hz and 4 °C. The linear viscoelastic (LVE) region of pure FG-film forming solution was located at ~10% strain. The addition of 0.01% GL shifted the critical strain to 3.99% (Instruments n.d.). This suggests a reduced resistance to oscillatory deformation, possibly due to the disruption of the FG matrix by GL addition at this low concentration (Chiou et al. 2006). When the GL concentration increased to 0.05 and 0.1%, the critical strain of the FG/GL solutions increased and showed no significant difference from that of the pure FG film-forming solution. In addition, the G' at critical strain increased with higher GL concentrations, supporting the formation of a stronger network in the FG film-forming solutions (Chiou et al. 2006). When the strain exceeds the critical strain, the G' values begin to decrease, indicating that the gelatin network has started to break down (Derkach et al. 2024). In contrast, the addition of SA in FG film-forming solutions had negligible effect on the critical strain and G' at critical strain (Error! Reference source not found.), indicating that SA did not significantly alter the network structure. When comparing the effects of GL and SA on the rheological properties of FG film-forming solutions, GL improved the viscoelasticity of FG film-forming

Fig. 3 FTIR spectra of the FG film forming solutions prepared using SA and GL at different concentrations (0.01, 0.05, 0.1% v/v)

Table 3 FTIR spectra characteristics of FG solutions with and without addition of SA and GL

Region	FG (cm ⁻¹)	FG+SA (cm ⁻¹)	FG+GL (cm ⁻¹)	Band Assignment
Amide A	3301	3301	3301	N-H and O-H stretching vibrations
Amide I	1652	1652	1654	C=O stretching of peptide linkages
Amide II	1544	1544	1546	N-H bending and C-N stretching
Amide III	1243	1243	1243	C-N stretching and N-H bending

solutions, while SA had no significant effect. This difference could be attributed to the distinct properties of GL and SA. GL can form a gel upon cooling after heating, whereas SA alone cannot form a gel at the concentrations investigated (Sow et al. 2019a; Petcharat 2017). SA cannot form a gel without the presence of Ca²⁺, which acts

as salt bridge to crosslink the negatively charged alginate chains (Sow et al. 2019a). High concentrations (0.05%, 0.1%) of GL stabilized the network of FG, resulting in an increased G', while the presence of SA interfered with the gel transition of FG, resulting the G' reduction (Sow et al. 2019a) (Table 2).

FTIR analysis

Figure 3 shows the FTIR spectra and Table 3 represents FTIR spectra characteristics of FG film-forming solutions with SA and GL at different concentrations. The spectrum of all FG solutions showed a similar pattern, which indicates that there were no major changes in functional groups of FG solutions due to interaction between FG and these polysaccharides. FG film-forming solution exhibited absorption bands at 3301 cm⁻¹ (amide A), 1652 cm⁻¹ (amide I), 1545 cm⁻¹ (amide II), and 1243 cm⁻¹ (amide III) (Nilsuwan et al. 2016a; Aewsiri

et al. 2009; Staroszczyk et al. 2014). However, the amide I is the most useful peak for infrared analysis, as it is influenced by both hydrogen bonding and the conformation of the protein (Pranoto et al. 2007; Park et al. 2021; Sow et al. 2019b). According to Gaussian components, the peak of amide I was located at 1652 cm^{-1} , indicating the predominant random coil in the FG solution structure (Sow et al. 2019a). The addition of GL at 0.05% and 0.1% (v/v) slightly shifted the peak of amide I to higher wavenumbers from 1652 to 1654 cm^{-1} , indicating that there was a change in the coupling of COO^- groups with the amide groups of gelatin (Pranoto et al. 2007). Similar shift caused by adding GL into tilapia FG was observed by Sow et al. (2019) where they observed a shift from 1657 – 1664 cm^{-1} in FG and GL mixtures (Sow et al. 2019b). Pranoto et al. (2007) reported that, the incorporation of 2 g of GL per 100 g of gelatin granules into 5% (w/v) tilapia FG films caused a slight shift in the amide I peak from 1656 to 1654 cm^{-1} (Pranoto et al. 2007). The addition of SA generally did not cause a significant shift in the amide I peak, which aligns with the finding of Sow et al. (2019), who reported that the amide I peak remained stable at 1660 cm^{-1} even with increasing SA concentrations in tilapia FG 6% (w/v) (Sow et al. 2019a). Several studies have investigated how polysaccharides affect the amide I peak of FG. Snow et al. (2018) found that in a mixture of κ -carrageenan and tilapia FG at a 4:96 (w/w) ratio, the deconvolution of the amide I spectra showed an increased helix/coil ratio compared to pure FG, suggesting a more structured conformation (Sow et al. 2018). Similarly, Chen et al. (2024) reported that adding chitosan, carrageenan, and sodium alginate to tilapia FG increased the peak intensity of the amide I band in gelatin-polysaccharide films, indicating a more ordered molecular structure (Chen et al. 2024). According to Fig. 3, the Amide A peak position remained stable after adding polysaccharides. However, while the intensity of the Amide A, Amide I, Amide II, and Amide III peaks showed little change with the addition of SA, the addition of 0.05% and 0.1% GL led to a noticeable decrease in their intensities. This effect could be attributed to a change in the hydration number (Grdadolnik 2003). Based on the rheological results, the mixture of FG and GL shifted toward a more stable state, which is normally observed in gel systems, suggesting a lower amount of free water in the FG–GL mixtures. Changes in hydration levels can modify the hydrogen-bond interactions within the protein structure (Grdadolnik 2003). Staroszczyk et al. (2014) observed the same phenomena in cold-water FG with the addition of chitosan. They found that the intensity of peaks including amide I, II, III in the region from 1700 cm^{-1} to 900 cm^{-1} decreased due to the formation of the two-component film (Staroszczyk et al. 2014). The Amide II peak showed a slight shift in wavenumber from

1544 cm^{-1} to 1551 cm^{-1} upon the addition of GL, whereas the FG–SA mixture exhibited no such change. This might be caused by the formation of hydrogen bond between OH groups of GL and NH groups of FG, affecting the stretching vibration of C–N and N–H bond of FG. Moreover, the study also reported that the shift of the peak of amide II from 1518 cm^{-1} to 1525 cm^{-1} in films including a cold-water FG with chitosan indicated the electrostatic interaction between the COO^- of FG and NH_3^+ of chitosan (Staroszczyk et al. 2014). The peak observed at the wavenumber of 1243 cm^{-1} in these solutions presented to amide III. According to Pyne et al. (2020), the amide III is associated with the stretching vibration of C–N and C–C, bending vibration of N–H and C–H (Frost et al. 2013; Niluwan et al. 2016b; Das et al. 2017). Especially, Amide III was very sensitive to the secondary structure of protein and was not affected by water absorption (Frost et al. 2013). The stability of Amide III peak suggests that film-forming solutions remain a random coil structure (Table 3).

Conclusions

In this study, the potential of FG blending with polysaccharides (GL and SA) to overcome the inherent limitations of FG as an alternative material for packaging were investigated. The films' properties, including mechanical, barrier, and rheological properties were analyzed. In conclusion, the mechanical and barrier properties of FG films could be improved by blending with GL/SA. However, the effect depended on the type of polysaccharides and concentrations. GL addition improved the film strength (TS) and barrier against water vapor (WVTR) regardless of the concentrations, making it suitable for packaging requiring high strength. High concentration of SA (0.1% v/v) improved the stretchability of the film (EB) although it hampered the film strength. For optimal barrier properties, SA at 0.05% (v/v) is recommended, exhibiting the improvement of 39% in the barrier properties of films compared to pure FG films. Rheological analysis showed that the addition of GL (0.05% and 0.1% v/v) increased both the storage modulus (G') and the loss modulus (G'') of the FG film-forming solutions, while SA had no significant effect on these parameters. Correspondingly, FTIR results revealed a shift of the Amide I and Amide II peak to higher wavenumbers with GL addition, indicating changes in molecular interactions, whereas the addition of SA did not cause any noticeable shift. Overall, GL addition showed more enhancing effect of FG film properties than SA, with the most promising formulation of blending FG with 0.1% GL.

Institutional Review Board Statement

Not applicable.

Sample Availability

Samples of the compounds are not available from the authors.

Authors' contributions

Conceptualization, N.S.; methodology, N.S., I.S., and T.T.T.N.; software, I.S. and T.T.T.N.; validation, N.S., I.S. and T.T.T.N.; formal analysis, T.T.T.N., N.S., and I.S.; writing-original draft preparation, T.T.T.N., writing-review and editing, I.S. and N.S., supervision, N.S. and I.S., project administration, N.S.; funding acquisition, N.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding

Open access funding provided by Nofima the food research institute. This research was funded by the EcoFISHent project ("Demonstrable and replicable cluster implementing systemic solutions through multilevel circular value chains for eco-efficient valorization of fishing and fish industries side-streams") belonging to Horizon 2020 Program—Green Deal (Innovation Action, Grant agreement ID: 101036428).

Data availability

Not applicable.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Competing interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Received: 12 August 2025 / Accepted: 5 February 2026

Published online: 17 February 2026

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